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WATERBORNE POLYURETHANE-UREA BASED COMPOSITE INKS FOR 3D PRINTING WITH ENHANCED PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Composite inks valid for Direct Ink Writing (DIW) 3D printing have been prepared using a waterborne polyurethane-urea (WBPUU) as matrix, κ -carrageenan as rheological modulator and graphene as nanoreinforcement. The rheological characterization of the inks proved strong dependence on their formulation, with inks prepared with 2 wt.% of carrageenan presenting the most suitable properties for DIW, which was clearly evidenced by the high shape fidelity shown by 3D printed parts obtained from these inks. Properties of the printed parts were not only related to their formulation, but also to the additives’ incorporation route. In this regard, inks prepared by in-situ addition showed highly reinforced properties, signaling to favored formation of WBPUU/additives interactions by this method. For supplying electrical conductivity, the presence of graphene in the material was not sufficient, since it seemed to remain embedded in the WBPUU matrix, and, thus, the application of a graphene coating was necessary.

Keywords: waterborne polyurethane–urea; 3D printing; graphene; bio-based scaffolds.

1. INTRODUCTION

After its creation in the early 1980s, 3D printing disrupted the traditional manufacturing industry and has since experienced constant growth, continuously improving its technology, accessibility and printing materials. 3D printing is a type of additive manufacturing method, in which objects are produced in a layer-by-layer fabrication process, following a computer-aided design (CAD). Its capacity to produce tailor-made on demand objects has made it extremely popular for many fields on applications, such as energy storage, tissue engineering, automotive, aerospace, drug delivery or sensors among others [1–5]. Recently, among the many different types of 3D printing technologies, Direct Ink Writing (DIW) has been gaining popularity, owing to its ability to produce complex 3D printed parts without the need of high temperatures or UV-exposure [6, 7]. However, inks with very specific rheological properties are needed in order to achieve a successful printing process [8, 9]. For instance, inks must show shear-thinning behavior, being able to flow under an applied stress (when extruded) but remaining structured at rest. Furthermore, inks with high-enough storage modulus values are needed, able to sustain the weight on top layers, as well as inks with yield points high-enough not to flow at rest but low-enough to allow extrusion. In this regard, natural polymers are some of the most used materials in 3D printing, thanks to their ability to retain large amounts of water, forming hydrogels, and showing great rheological behavior. Among them alginate, collagen and gelatin are some of the most common ones [9]. However, these materials often show poor mechanical behavior, which extremely restricts their fields of applications [10]. Therefore, the preparation of inks with a polymer, natural or synthetic, or a mix based of them, with better mechanical properties, such as higher load resistance and lower brittleness, could be of great interest.

An answer to the aforementioned problem could be found in the use of waterborne polyurethane-urea (WBPUU) based inks, as demonstrated in previous work [11–13]. Polyurethane-ureas are segmented polymers, which show a wide and easily-tunable range of properties [14–16]. Moreover, polyurethane-ureas can be successfully prepared using environmentally friendly precursors, resulting in partially or fully bio-based polymers [17–20]. WBPUU not only avoid the use of volatile organic compounds in its synthesis, but also result in the polymer in an aqueous dispersion, which could be extremely beneficial for different reasons, such as the easy incorporation of hydrophilic nanostructures [21–23] and their shown

biocompatibility [13, 24]. However, the rheological behavior of WBPUU dispersions is often inadequate to be used in DIW 3D printing, thus they need to be modulated by addition of other components [7, 24].

As previously stated, natural polymers can result in inks with excellent rheological properties. Thus, inks prepared with a mix of WBPPU and a natural polymer could benefit from the mechanical properties of the first and the rheological properties of the latter. Carrageenan is another natural polymer capable of forming gel structure, it is a very high molecular weight natural polymer (with an average molecular weight of over 100 kDa [25, 26]), which shows biocompatibility, non-toxicity and low cost [25, 27, 28]. Carrageenan could be of great interest for 3D printing, since it has been reported that its presence and content can affect solutions' rheological behavior [29], thus, it could be used to modulate the rheology of the prepared inks. Moreover, its thixotropic behavior makes it a perfect option for DIW [30].

The use of nanoentities for ink preparation shows also very promising results. The addition of nanoentities does not only help modulate the ink's rheological behavior, but can also reinforce the material's properties [12, 22]. Carbonaceous materials can be used in inks production, resulting in materials with enhanced mechanical properties and supplied with electrical conductivity. Valentin et al. prepared alginate/graphene oxide inks which showed enhanced stability and resulted in final printed parts with improved mechanical properties and chemical stability [31]. Li et al. observed that the addition of graphene to an alginate matrix improved its thixotropic behavior and allowed for 3D printed parts with better shape fidelity [32]. Ajiteru et al. prepared silk graphene bioinks, which showed electrical and biological properties that support cell proliferation and its neurogenic activity [33]. In previous works, carbonaceous structures, such as graphene and graphene oxide, have been successfully used as a nanoreinforcement for a WBPUU matrix [13, 34].

Thus, in this work, the possibility of preparing nanocomposite inks with enhanced properties and valid for DIW 3D printing was analyzed. To do so, a partially bio-based waterborne polyurethane-urea was used as matrix, carrageenan was employed as rheological modulator and graphene was added for reinforcing purposes. The effect of the components' content and incorporation route on the ink's properties and on the final material's properties was studied, regarding their rheological behavior, printability, morphology and thermal, mechanical and electrical behavior.

2. MATERIALS

For WBPUU synthesis, soft-segment forming renewable sourced difunctional polyol (Priplast 3192[®], Mw= 2000 g mol⁻¹) was purchased from Croda. Hard-segment composing isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI, DESMODOUR I) and ethylene diamine (EDA) were supplied by Covestro and Fluka, respectively. 2,2-Bis(hydroxymethyl)propionic acid (DMPA, Aldrich) was employed as internal emulsifier, and triethylamine (TEA, Fluka), as neutralizing agent. Dibutyltin dilaurate, used as catalyst, was purchased from Aldrich.

κ -carrageenan (Lot. #BCBX5072) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Graphite flakes (Aldrich) used during the preparation of graphene were purchased from Aldrich, whereas employed sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), sodium nitrate (NaNO₃), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were supplied by Panreac. Finally, *Salvia officinalis L.* was purchased at a local herbalist.

2.1. Synthesis of the waterborne polyurethane urea and graphene

The WBPUU and graphene (G) were prepared following procedures described in a previous work [34]. Briefly, the synthesis of the polyurethane-urea (polyol/DMPA/IPDI/EDA molar ratio of 1/1.1/3.5/0.6) was carried out in a four-necked jacketed reactor, armed with a thermocouple, a nitrogen inlet and a mechanical stirrer. The synthesis was performed in a two-step polymerization process. In the first step, the OH/NCO reaction took place, letting the isocyanate react first with the previously dried polyol polyol at 90 °C for 3 hours and then with the DMPA (previously neutralized with TEA) at 50 °C for 1 hour, forming a prepolymer. In the second step, the phase inversion was carried out, by dropwise addition of deionized water, as well as the chain extension, by reaction of NH₂/NCO of the newly added EDA and the remaining NCO groups in the isocyanate and the prepolymer. This last reaction was done at 35 °C for 2 hours. Finally an aqueous dispersion was obtained with a polyurethane-urea solid content of 33 wt.%.

For the preparation of graphene, first graphene oxide was prepared from the modified Hummer's method and later it was reduced to eliminate the oxygenated groups. Graphene oxide was obtained parting from graphite. First 1 g of graphite, 0.5 g of NaNO₃ and 23 mL of H₂SO₄ were mixed in an ice bath for 30 minutes under magnetic agitation, following this, 3 g of KMnO₄ was added and the mixture was let to react for 2 more hours in the ice bath. The temperature was then raised to 35 °C and 46 mL of water was added dropwise. The mixture was moved to an oil bath at 98 °C and left for 30 minutes to oxidize, after which, 10 mL of H₂O₂ was added dropwise. The mixture was then cooled down and cleaned in a centrifugation process. After filtering and drying, graphite oxide was obtained, which was then sonicated with a probe

sonicator for 3 hours and centrifuged at 4000 rpm, to obtain the smaller fractions; and was once again filtered and left to dry, obtaining graphene oxide. In order to reduce it to graphene, a thermal process was employed. Graphene oxide was introduced to an oven at 500 °C for 30 minutes, where most of the oxygen-containing groups were eliminated.

Since graphene is highly hydrophobic, in order to disperse it in water the use of a surfactant was necessary. In this regard a natural extract, *Salvia* extract, has shown great capacities, owing to its great affinity with graphene, caused by its phenolic moieties forming π - π interactions with graphene and increasing the stability of the dispersion [35]. *Salvia* extracts were obtained from infusion method [36], in which 20 g of the dried plant were added to 800 mL of boiling distilled water for 5-10 minutes. The suspension was then filtered and freeze-dried to obtain *Salvia* extract in powder form.

2.2. Inks preparation

WBPUU/CAR and WBPUU/G/CAR nanocomposite inks were prepared using two incorporation methods, ex-situ and in-situ. For ex-situ nanocomposite inks, first, *Salvia* extract was added to the polyurethane dispersion, acting as a surfactant to improve dispersion of graphene, with a ratio of 1:1 for G:*Salvia*. Afterwards, G was added and was dispersed with an ultraturrax homogenizer (Polytron PT 2500E, KINEMATICA) for 20-25 minutes at 10000 rpm, and last, carrageenan was added and mixed for another 10 minutes. High shear stirring was carried out in an iced bath, in order to avoid high temperatures and degradation of the systems.

For in-situ preparation, *Salvia*, G and carrageenan were added and mixed in water, following a similar process to the above described one. *Salvia* was first dissolved in water and graphene was then added and dispersed using an ultraturrax homogenizer (10 minutes, 10000 rpm), followed by carrageenan incorporation and further agitation for 10 minutes. Components were added mixed in water to the WBPUU synthesis during the phase inversion step.

Different contents of carrageenan (1 and 2 wt.%) and graphene (0.5 and 1 wt.%) were used to prepare inks (Table 1). Nanocomposite inks were named as “xGyCAR_{EX}” or “xGyCAR_{IN}” for ex-situ and in-situ prepared inks, respectively, and where “x” denotes the content of G and “y” the content of carrageenan.

For comparative purposes, a gel without polyurethane, composed of only carrageenan, *Salvia* and graphene dispersed in water (M-0.5G2CAR) was prepared.

Table 1. Composition of WBPUU/CAR/G inks

Sample	Preparation method	Content of G (wt. %)	Content of <i>Salvia</i> (wt.%)	Content of CAR (wt. %)
2CAR _{EX}	ex-situ	-	-	2
0.5G1CAR _{EX}	ex-situ	0.5	0.5	1
0.5G2CAR _{EX}	ex-situ	0.5	0.5	2
1G1CAR _{EX}	ex-situ	1	1	1
1CAR _{IN}	in-situ	-	-	1
2CAR _{IN}	in-situ	-	-	2
0.5G2CAR _{IN}	in-situ	0.5	0.5	2
1G1CAR _{IN}	in-situ	1	1	1
M-0.5G2CAR	-	0.5	0.5	2

2.3. 3D Printing

Inks were processed in an adapted Tumaker Voladora 3D printing, at a printing speed of 6 mm·s⁻¹, with a 0.8 mm nozzle and working at room temperature. The printed parts were subsequently submitted to a freeze-drying process in order to obtain porous scaffolds.

As printing design, a cylinder was chosen ($\varnothing = 10$ mm and h = 5 mm). Printed parts were named as “3D-X”, where “X” is the name of their corresponding inks.

3. CHARACTERIZATION

3.1. Rheological properties

For rheological characterization, a Haake Viscotester iQ (Thermo Scientific) was employed, working at room temperature and using a plate-plate geometry (P35/Al adapter, $\varnothing_{\text{plate}} = 35$ mm and gap = 1 mm). For neat WBPUU dispersion, a coaxial cylinder geometry was used (CC25 DIN/Ti adapter), with a piston radius of 12.54 mm and a ring gap of 1.06 mm.

Three types of tests were performed, flow tests, spectromechanical test and structure recovery tests.

Flow tests were carried out in rotational test, in a shear rate range from 0.2 to 1000 s⁻¹. From this curves, flow index (n) value of each ink was calculated from Power Law (equation 1).

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = K\dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (\text{equation 1})$$

where η is the viscosity (Pa·s), $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate (s^{-1}), K is the consistency index (Pa·sⁿ) and n is the flow index (dimensionless).

From these curves, viscosity at different shear rates was also determined, at the lowest shear rate tested ($0.2 s^{-1}$), at $100 s^{-1}$ and at the shear rate the inks are submitted to during the printing process in the nozzle, labeled as $\dot{\gamma}_n$. For the calculation on the last one, it was necessary to consider the effect of the inks non-Newtonian behavior, since it will cause the flow on a capillary to deviate from a parabolic velocity profile [32]. Hence, for the correct calculation of the shear rate during the printing process, the use of equation 2 is necessary.

$$\dot{\gamma}_n^n = \left[\frac{V \cdot R^2}{\left(\frac{n}{3n+1}\right) \left(R^{\frac{3n+1}{n}}\right)} \right]^n \cdot r \quad (\text{equation 2})$$

where $\dot{\gamma}_n$ is the shear rate the ink is submitted to at the nozzle, n is the flow index calculated from Power Law, V is the printing speed, r is any distance located between the center of the nozzle and its radius and R is the radius of the nozzle.

Spectromechanical tests, used for yield point (YP) determination, were performed in oscillatory mode, in a shear stress range of 10 to 1000 Pa. Yield point and flow point (FP) were determined as the point of deviation of G' from linearity, as proposed by Cyriac et al. [37], and the crossover point for G' and G'' , respectively.

Last, structure recovery tests were performed in a three-stage experiment, where the capacity of inks to recover their initial viscosity after being submitted to a high shear rate stage was assessed. In the first and third step, viscosity was measured in rotary mode at $0.2 s^{-1}$ during 100 s, and in the second step at $100 s^{-1}$. Structural recovery capacity of the inks was calculated using equation 3.

$$\text{Structural Recovery} = \frac{\eta_{AS}}{\eta_{BS}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{equation 3})$$

where η_{BS} is the viscosity of the material before the high shear rate process and η_{AS} is the viscosity after the high shear rate process; in both cases the viscosity was measured after 60 seconds of the beginning of that part of the test.

3.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The morphology of the final 3D printed parts was observed by SEM, using Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEG-SEM) Hitachi S-4800N, at a voltage of 5 kV. For this, a transversal section of the samples was analyzed, after being cryofractured in liquid nitrogen and sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold (~ 10 nm) in an Emitech K550X ion sputter.

Pore diameters were measured using ImageJ software and averaged out of 50 measurements.

3.3. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal behavior of the 3D printed neat WBPUU and composites were determined by DSC, for which a Mettler Toledo DSC 3+ equipment was employed, provided with an electric intracooler as refrigerator unit. Samples were prepared using aluminum pans (5-10 mg) and a heating scan, ranging from -65 to 200 °C, was carried out at 10 °C min⁻¹ in nitrogen atmosphere.

From the obtained thermograms, the glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined, as the inflection point of the heat capacity change, an order-disorder transition temperature (T_{HS}) was determined as the maximum of the endothermic peak, related to the short range ordering of the hard segment, and its corresponding enthalpy, as the area below the peak.

3.4. Compression tests

The mechanical properties of the 3D printed parts were analyzed by compression tests, using an Instron 5967 universal testing machine, provided with a 500 N load cell. 3D printed cylinders were compressed to a fixed length of 2 mm at a crosshead speed of 10 mm min⁻¹, working at room temperature.

Compression modulus was calculated as the slope of the stress-strain curve at low deformations, the stress was measured at the maximum applied strain (60%) and densification strain as the strain at the intersection point between the stress plateau and a line extrapolated from the densification line. Five specimens of each system were tested and averaged. Specific Young modulus values were measured as the ratio between each sample's Young modulus and its density, which was calculated as the ratio between their measured weight and volume.

3.5. Electrical properties

In order to measure the electrical conductivity of printed parts, two-point measurements were carried out in a Keithley 4200-SCS (Keithley Instruments, Cleveland, USA) equipment for semiconductor analysis. Tests were performed for a 0–5 V linear scans, with 0.01 V step and compliance of 0.1 A. Electrical resistance (R) was calculated from intensity-voltage curves.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Characterization of the inks

In order to analyze the rheological behavior of the prepared inks, first, shear rate vs. viscosity curves were obtained (Figure 1). Viscosity values measured at different shear rates, as well as calculated flow index, are summarized in Table 2.

For a correct 3D printing process, inks must show shear-thinning behavior, so their viscosity is low when being extruded, but high, and able to retain shape, at rest [38, 39]. As can be observed, all systems show shear-thinning behavior, with $n < 1$ values and with viscosity decreasing as shear rate increases.

Results show that the addition of new components strongly affects the viscosity of the systems, as can be seen by the big increase of this property when comparing composite inks to neat WBPUU dispersion. The content of carrageenan strongly affects the rheological behavior of the material, with inks with higher CAR content showing higher viscosity values. This same effect is observed for *Salvia* and carbonaceous reinforcement concentration, though more subtle, with viscosity values slightly increasing with reinforcement concentration. The gel formation capacity of carrageenan and the reinforcement supplied from graphene impeding inks' flow result in inks with better potential for DIW when high contents of these components are used. Moreover, it can be observed that the content of G plays a bigger role in gels with lower CAR content, since in gels with high carrageenan content the gelling effect of this component is predominant over the effect produced by graphene, in agreement with literature reports [40]. This can be clearly seen by comparing 0.5G1CAR_{EX} and 1G1CAR_{EX}, whereas in more concentrated CAR gels, comparing 2CAR_{EX} and 0.5G2CAR_{EX}, it does not affect the rheological behavior as much.

Regarding the incorporation method, it was observed that in-situ addition results in inks with lower viscosity values than their ex-situ prepared homologues. In ex-situ addition, the added components are not able to easily approach the already synthesized WBPUU particles, and CAR molecules are more likely

to interact with water, which allows for a better gel formation. On in-situ addition, on the other hand, the addition of the new components during the particle formation step and the strong agitation allow the proximity of the components, and result in additives, both CAR and G, partially placed inside the WBPUU particles, which favors matrix/additives interactions and hinders interactions with water. This fact was previously observed in a similar study when working with cellulose nanofibers [12]. Moreover, despite the phase inversion and chain extension steps of the synthesis being carried out at low temperatures in order to favor NCO and NH₂ reaction, it is possible that in in-situ addition some OH groups of additives might react with NCO groups, forming chemical bonds.

Overall, the higher viscosity shown by gels with 2 wt.% of carrageenan may be favorable for a satisfactory printing process.

Figure 1. Viscosity flow curves for WBPUU/CAR/G inks

Table 2. Viscosity and rheological parameters for neat WBPUU and ex-situ and in-situ prepared WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

Sample	η at 0.2 s^{-1} (Pa·s)	η at γ_n (Pa·s)	η at 100 s^{-1} (Pa·s)	n
WBPUU	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.725
2CAR _{EX}	831.8	68.4	4.1	0.041
0.5G1CAR _{EX}	167.6	6.4	0.8	0.186
0.5G2CAR _{EX}	1388.0	64.2	4.4	0.137
1G1CAR _{EX}	958.0	56.6	4.0	0.139
1CAR _{IN}	27.5	1.8	0.5	0.374
2CAR _{IN}	271.8	11.8	2.2	0.287

0.5G2CAR_{IN}	935.9	26.4	3.2	0.162
1G1CAR_{IN}	89.3	6.1	1.3	0.380
M-0.5G2CAR	849.3	38.5	2.3	0.082

Spectromechanical analysis were also performed (Figure 2), in order to observed the gel-like behavior of the inks and determine their yield and flow points. Measured values are shown in Table 3.

It can be observed that neither WBPUU dispersion nor 1CAR_{IN} ink show gel-like behavior, presenting higher G'' than G' values throughout the stress scan. The low amount of carrageenan in 1CAR_{IN}, plus its complete lack of *Salvia* and graphene, are responsible for its inability to form a gel structure. This ink does not show the rheological behavior required for a 3D printing process, thus, it was discarded, as was the neat WBPUU dispersion.

Figure 2. Storage (solid line) and loss (dotted line) moduli as a function of shear stress of neat WBPUU and ex-situ and in-situ prepared WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

It can be observed that the content of carrageenan is a key parameter in the strength of the gels, with systems with higher CAR content showing higher yield and flow points. Carrageenan has been reported to be able to form strong gel structures in water [41, 42], in agreement with this are the highest yield and flow points shown by M-0.5G2CAR. However, the weaker gel-like structures obtained when the WBPUU matrix or graphene are present indicates that they hinder the gel formation capacity of carrageenan, resulting in gels with lower YP and FP.

In agreement with the previous assessment, among WBPUU containing composite inks 2CAR_{EX} and 2CAR_{IN} show the highest yield and flow points, owing to their high carrageenan content and lack of graphene and *Salvia* hampering direct water/carrageenan and polyurethane-urea/carrageenan interactions, which allows the formation of a better gel structure. On the contrary, inks prepared with 1 wt.% of carrageenan show weaker gel behavior. Among ex-situ preparations, 0.5G1CAR_{EX} shows the lowest yield and flow points, beginning to flow and behaving like a liquid at very low shear stress values. For in-situ preparations, as previously noted, 1CAR_{IN} does not show a gel-like behavior and 1G1CAR_{IN} ink shows significantly low values.

Agreeing with viscosity results, it is worth noting that in-situ preparation results in less gelled structures, once again suggesting more direct water/carrageenan interactions in ex-situ prepared systems.

The defined yield point of the inks, more prominent for inks containing 2 wt.% of carrageenan, may result in better shape fidelity when used in 3D printing, as suggested by literature reports [22, 43]. Moreover, higher contents of CAR and G increase the storage modulus values, and these reinforced structures will be more likely to support the given shape and the weight of the top layers of the 3D printed part without collapsing.

The structural recovery capacity of the inks was also tested, in order to analyze the thixotropic behavior of the material. Obtained curves are shown in Figure 3 and calculated values in Table 3. Ideally, ink viscosity should drop instantly when a shear stress is applied (while being extruded) and will recover fast enough to hold shape and hold the weight of latter layers [32].

Figure 3 shows the instant drop of viscosity when systems were submitted to a high shear rate, showing their capacity to flow during the extrusion process. Furthermore, when shear rate is once again lowered, the ability of inks' viscosity to increase again is shown. However, results show that recovery capacity of the inks is related to their formulation. Systems containing only carrageenan and polyurethane show high recovery values, which point to a promising shape fidelity, whereas for systems with graphene and *Salvia*, this capacity is strongly deteriorated. The presence of these components strongly hinders the capacity of carrageenan to reform interactions, which could affect the shape fidelity of objects printed with these inks.

Figure 3. Structure recovery tests of WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

Table 3. Yield and flow point values and structure recovery capacity of WBPUU/G/CAR inks

Sample	Yield Point (MPa)	Flow Point (MPa)	Structural Recovery (%)
2CAR_{EX}	98.8	241.8	84 ± 8
0.5G1CAR_{EX}	11.3	22.1	53 ± 26
0.5G2CAR_{EX}	69.8	242.1	63 ± 9
1G1CAR_{EX}	39.8	188.1	59 ± 11
2CAR_{IN}	43.0	89.1	91 ± 3
0.5G2CAR_{IN}	18.5	65.1	64 ± 5
1G1CAR_{IN}	12.3	20.3	54 ± 3
M-0.5G2CAR	160.7	291.4	59 ± 15

The 3D printing process of the inks will be dependent on their rheological behavior, and though all inks show the necessary shear-thinning behavior, the differences in their ability to flow and retain the given shape when needed will strongly affect this production process. In this regard, inks containing 2 wt.% are expected to show the best results, ought to their great gel-like behavior and fast recovery capacity.

4.2. Characterization of the 3D printed parts

Inks were employed to produce 3D printed cylinders by DIW 3D printing and obtained printed parts are shown in Figure 4.

It can be observed that regardless of the preparation method, systems containing 2 wt.% of carrageenan show the best shape fidelity, as previously suggested by their rheological properties, being these systems

the ones showing the strongest gel behavior. The low tendency to flow at rest and the capacity to support weight of top layers exhibited by 2CAR_{EX}, 0.5G2CAR_{EX}, 2CAR_{IN} and 0.5G2CAR_{IN} result in a great printing capacity, proving the adequate rheological behavior of these inks for DIW.

On the other hand, inks with poor rheological behavior resulted in parts with poor shape fidelity, as shown by 1G1CAR_{EX} and 1G1CAR_{IN}, whose more liquid-like behavior result in 3D printed parts with poor shape fidelity. 0.5G1CAR_{EX} showed extremely poor precision when 3D printed, caused by its low viscosity and storage modulus allowing it to flow and impeding it from maintaining the given shape. Thus, 3D printed parts obtained from this ink were discarded.

Figure 4. 3D-printed cylinders obtained from WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

In order to analyse the internal morphology of the printed parts, SEM analysis of a cross section of the parts were carried out. Obtained micrographies for 3D printed parts obtained from ex-situ and in-situ preparations are shown in Figure 5.

For 3D printed parts obtained from ex-situ prepared inks, it can be observed that 3D-2CAR_{EX} shows the most homogeneous morphology. It presents a spherical porous comprised structure, with an average porous diameter of 45.4 ± 9.1 μm . However, for compositions containing graphene and *Salvia*, changes on the morphology take place. For 3D-0.5G2CAR_{EX} a mix morphology is observed, where bigger and slightly more elongated pores are present, with an average length of 142.8 ± 30.6 μm and width of 44.2 ± 3.8 μm , as well as some spherical pores with an average diameter of 67.0 ± 13.2 μm . For 3D-1G1CAR_{EX}

spherical pores were observed once again ($\emptyset = 55.4 \pm 7.4 \mu\text{m}$), however, in this case the pores were less defined and showing a more open structure.

The changes in morphology can be attributed to the water present in the systems. Two types of water can be found in hydrogels, free and bonded water, which will have an impact in the porosity of the systems. For 3D-2CAR_{EX}, due to the high amount of interactions between the carrageenan and the water, the amount of free water was low. However, these interactions were altered by the addition of G and *Salvia*. New interactions formed between the carrageenan and the new components will result in more free water. The liberation of each type of water will strongly alter the pores sizes and shape in each system, resulting in materials with overall bigger pores when more free water is present [44].

For parts obtained from in-situ preparations, overall, larger pores are observed. As previously suggested in rheological studies, in-situ preparations promote interaction between polyurethane-urea, carrageenan, *Salvia* extract and remaining oxidized groups in the reduced graphene oxide structure, instead of with water. As a result, there is a larger amount of free water present on the hydrogels. The resulting morphology is attributed to the removal of this free water by freeze-drying. 3D printed parts obtained from in-situ ink show elongated pores. 3D-2CAR_{IN} exhibits pores with a length of $303.0 \pm 37.8 \mu\text{m}$ and a width of $72.7 \pm 13.9 \mu\text{m}$, for 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN} the pore size increases to 433.9 ± 60.2 and $78.4 \pm 7.5 \mu\text{m}$, and lastly for 3D-1G1CAR_{IN} pores of $417.8 \pm 62.9 \times 65.9 \pm 8.9 \mu\text{m}$ are observed.

When inks with poor rheological properties are printed, crushing of cell wall can take place, due to their inability to hold the weight of the top layers [12]. However, this was not the case for the printed composites inks, where, thought, elongated pores are observed, there is no sign any trouble supporting top layers, since no signs of wall crushing could be observed in the micrographies. The strong gel formation capacity of carrageenan and great reinforcing effect of graphene prove to have great capacity against this phenomenon.

For 3D-M-0.5GCAR, a very different morphology is seen, with a more open cell structure, governed by the presence of pores. It is worth noting, that without WBPUU the total solid content was significantly lower, being the content of water to be removed significantly higher and the density of the 3D printed part much lower.

Figure 5. SEM images of 3D printed parts from WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

Thermal behavior of the different systems were studied by DSC. The measured T_{gSS} , T_{HS} and ΔH_{HS} values are summarized in Table 4. Though all systems show relatively similar T_g values, around $-50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, small changes regarding the short range ordering transition of the hard segment can be observed.

A significant increase of the enthalpy takes place with the addition of carrageenan, graphene and salvia extract, compared to the neat WBPUU. The interactions that have formed between the matrix and the *Salvia* and the remaining oxidized groups present in graphene, together with the presence of carrageenan result in structures with higher transition temperatures and enthalpies, as is often observed for bonded WBPUUs [45].

Regarding the incorporation route, for in-situ prepared nanocomposites, higher T_{HS} and ΔH_{HS} were measured, agreeing with the previous suggestion of favored matrix/reinforcement interactions and chemical bond formations by in-situ addition method.

Table 4. Thermal properties observed from the DSC curves for neat WBPUU and 3D printed parts obtained from WBPUU/CAR and WBPUU/G/CAR inks

Sample	T_g ($^\circ\text{C}$)	T_{HS} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	ΔH_{HS} ($\text{J}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
WBPUU	-49.1	74.7	9.0
3D-2CAR	-48.7	78.3	17.5
3D-0.5G2CAR_{EX}	-49.0	78.7	17.6
3D-1G1CAR_{EX}	-51.1	80.7	21.0
3D-2CAR_{IN}	-47.7	89.0	19.0
3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}	-48.4	86.0	19.8
3D-1G1CAR_{IN}	-49.7	83.0	21.2

The mechanical behavior of the printed parts was tested in compression tests and obtained stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 6. In Table 5 calculated and measured values are summarized, namely density, specific Young modulus, stress at 60% strain and densification strain values.

All systems show stress-strain curves comprised of three section: 1) elastic zone, where the material is able to fully recovered the suffered deformation, 2) plastic zone, where the walls start to buckle and the porous structure begins collapsing irreparably, and 3) densification zone: where the cell walls are crushed and the materials behave like a non-porous solid [46, 47].

Figure 6. Stress-strain curves from compression tests for WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR 3D printed parts

It can be observed that both the composition and preparation method play an important part on the mechanical properties of the final material. For ex-situ preparations, it can be seen that 3D-2CAR system shows higher modulus and stress values than systems containing graphene. The poor reinforcements effect supplied by graphene in this case could be attributed to two factors. On the one hand, the addition of graphene could have interfered in the formation of the gel structure, as seen previously on rheological and morphological analyses, and, thus, result in poorly structured materials. On the other hand, the harder homogenization process for these materials, and, in consequence, the longer high shear agitation process might have damaged graphene flakes, resulting in smaller flakes and, therefore, in worse reinforcement effect, as previously reported in literature for small fractions [48, 49].

3D printed parts obtained from in-situ prepared inks, show a very different behavior. In this case, materials with higher specific Young modulus and stress values are obtained when graphene and carrageenan are added, attributed to favored matrix/additives interactions and formed chemical bonds. Moreover, the shorter homogenization process needed in this preparation method does not significantly damage the graphene structure. For high amounts of graphene, the reinforcement effect can be clearly seen, with 3D-1G1CAR_{IN} showing enhanced mechanical properties, with high Young modulus, specific modulus and stress values, proving the characteristic reinforcement capacity of graphene [50–52].

For comparative purposes, the mechanical behavior of 3D-M-0.5GCAR was studied, where the great influence of polyurethane on the mechanical properties of the material is proven. 3D-M-0.5GCAR shows very different properties compared to WBPUU containing parts, showing significantly lower values of Young modulus and stress, due to the more brittle behavior of its governing carrageenan [53].

Table 5. Young modulus, specific Young modulus, stress at 60% strain and densification strain values for 3D printed parts obtained from WBPUU/CAR, WBPUU/G/CAR and G/CAR inks

Sample	Density (g·cm ⁻³)	Specific Young modulus (MPa·cm ³ ·g ⁻¹)	Stress at 60% strain (MPa)	Densification strain (MPa)
3D-2CAR	0.39 ± 0.05	60.6 ± 12.7	3.1 ± 0.2	48.9 ± 1.3
3D-0.5G2CAR_{EX}	0.38 ± 0.03	20.4 ± 5.4	1.4 ± 0.2	50.3 ± 0.5
3D-1G1CAR_{EX}	0.40 ± 0.01	30.9 ± 8.9	1.9 ± 0.1	51.8 ± 0.8
3D-2CAR_{IN}	0.39 ± 0.01	62.6 ± 5.3	2.6 ± 0.2	49.6 ± 0.3
3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}	0.38 ± 0.01	64.3 ± 9.3	2.1 ± 0.3	49.8 ± 1.0
3D-1G1CAR_{IN}	0.41 ± 0.02	92.8 ± 9.3	3.0 ± 0.3	50.7 ± 0.6
3D-M-0.5G2CAR	0.04 ± 0.01	9.4 ± 2.3	0.1 ± 0.0	48.9 ± 1.4

However, when testing the electrical conductivity of the materials, it was observed that they present extremely poor conductivity, with resistance values around 10⁹ Ω. This, however, is not the case for 3D printed part containing no polyurethane-urea (3D-M-0.5G2CAR), for which the resistance values measured are significantly lower, (56.0 ± 16.7) × 10⁶, showing values proper of a semiconductor. This indicates, that when polyurethane-urea is present in the formulation the conductive graphene stays embedded in the matrix and is not able to form a conductive network, as seen in a previous work [34]. As a solution to this issue, and willing to analyze the possibility of supplying electrical conductivity to the printing parts, the potential of applying a graphene coating was studied.

4.3. Coating of the 3D printed parts

For coating tests, 3D-2CAR_{IN} and 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN} were selected based on their good shape fidelity and shown properties. For the coating process, a previously optimized procedure was employed [34]. First, the 3D printed parts were submerged for a few seconds in NMP, to allow a better penetration of the coating, and then were sonicated for 15 minutes in a graphene in cyclohexane dispersion (10 mg mL⁻¹). Coated materials were then cleaned with distilled water and left to dry at room temperature. After coating process, 3D-2CAR_{IN} and 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN} were named 3D-2CAR_{IN}/G and 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}/G, respectively.

Electrical tests show both coated systems exhibit electrical conductive capacity, with resistance values of $(7.4 \pm 11.5) \times 10^6 \Omega$ and $(373.0 \pm 44.2) \times 10^6 \Omega$ for 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}/G and 3D-2CAR_{IN}/G, respectively.

The significantly higher conductivity shown by 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}/G could be due to a better adherence of the coating layer to the surface of the material, due to a good affinity of the coating with the remaining oxidized groups present in the surface of 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}.

SEM was once again used to analyze the morphology of the systems, in order to observed possible changes taken place after the coating process. Obtained images are shown in Figure 7, where the coating layer (Figure 7a-d) and the internal morphology of the systems (Figure 7e-f) can be seen.

Figure 7. SEM images of graphene-coated 3D printed parts

A successful coating process can be deduced, from the graphene shell observed in Figure 7a-d. As suggested by electrical test results, a better formed coat can be seen for 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}/G, showing higher thickness and homogeneity, once again pointing to a better affinity and coating adhesion. Nonetheless, it can be observed that after coating process the initial porous structure shown by the uncoated systems was damaged (Figure 7e). Nonetheless, 3D-0.5G2CAR_{IN}/G shows a slightly less damaged structure, with a more homogeneous structure, formed by relatively similarly shaped and homogeneously dispersed porous (Figure 7f). The graphene present in the structure might have helped protect the material and impede further damaging.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Obtained results show that WBPUU, carrageenan and graphene can be successfully used to prepare inks valid for DIW 3D printing. However, their success degree will be dependent on the composition of the ink. In this regard, inks with high amount of carrageenan (2 wt.%) show the best rheological behavior for DIW, due to their strong gel-like behavior at rest and their capacity to flow under stress. This was clearly observed in the shape fidelity of the 3D parts, where inks containing 2 wt.% of carrageenan resulted in parts with high shape accuracy.

However, properties of the final material proved to be extremely dependent on the incorporation route of the components. This was observed in the morphology of the parts, which varied depending the incorporation method,, ought to the favored interaction taking place in this method. The main difference, however, was observed in the measured mechanical properties, with in-situ preparations showing significantly more enhanced properties than ex-situ preparations, which can be attributed to a number of factors, namely the less damaged graphene nanostructures in this formulations, the favored interactions between components and the higher homogeneity achieved by this incorporation route. However, since systems showed no electrical conductive capacity, the use of a graphene coating was analyzed, which successfully results in conductive 3D printed parts, with slightly damaged structures.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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